

Design for all life

Guest editor,
Stanislav Roudavski

In many design situations, animals, plants, fungi, and bacteria are better clients than humans. These nonhuman beings live diverse, interesting, and grossly under-explored lives, making research exciting and new discoveries easy.

They are in control of real riches: energy, oxygen, and nutrients, rather than abstract dollar amounts. Importantly, nonhuman lifeforms innovate. All have forms of subjectivity, all communicate and process information, many have lasting cultures. All are successful, simply because they have survived. Today, millions of lifeforms experience human-caused extinctions. In most cases, complete remediation is impossible but remarkable improvements are accessible and morally imperative.

Engagement with nonhuman clients and collaborations can be challenging. They cannot read project briefs or assess drawings. Many live cryptic lives. Few have any commitment to human projects. Some actively resist surveillance or intrusion. However, these challenges should not prevent action. On the contrary, they reveal opportunities for improvements in ethics, politics, aesthetics, cultures, and technology.

To give some examples, design projects of our Deep Design Lab at the University of Melbourne investigate practical approaches to interspecies justice. For example, we have explored designing for nonhuman capabilities,¹ built habitat structures

that take inspiration from arboreal termite nests as shown on the next page, proposed smart systems to minimise environmental light pollution,² initiated a reconsideration of smart cities in more-than-human terms,³ and developed tools for more-than-human heritage.⁴

We find that more-than-human approaches to design can be compatible with human needs, creatively liberating and ethically upstanding. Every architect needs a client, but not all clients are rewarding. A powerful prince or a rich corporation might have the capacity for large-scale construction but an aversion to go beyond conventions or little commitment to the interests of others.

How does the collaboration with nonhumans relate to the current debates about the role of design? Many see human designers as the purveyors of progress. Designers support development and enable growth. Yet products of human ingenuity including writing, cities, and agriculture have enabled the global damage exacerbated by the ecological imperialism in recent history and the extractive economies of today. Techno-optimists advise further expansion through

deep-sea mining, geoengineering, extra-terrestrial manufacturing, and settlements on Mars. Design rooted in existing systems performs at large scales, but is it successful?

Unfortunately, many impacts of design are catastrophically destructive to life. Design rationalises, streamlines, standardises, and simplifies. It also extracts, pollutes, and induces excessive consumption. Geodiversity, biodiversity, cultural complexity – the richness of life on Earth and with it its wellbeing – diminish as a direct consequence of many current design practices.

Design's negative impacts have led to shifts in thinking. In densely populated Europe, a growing impulse is to abstain from new building and to reuse instead. The commitments to energy efficiency and forms of greening are also growing. But is mitigation enough? Will it be possible to reverse the obliteration of life by tweaking the extractive systems that – after all – are working as intended? Evidence shows that improvements within business-as-usual will not suffice.

Instead, we endorse a substantial restructuring of societies in more-than-human terms. A common way to argue for the importance of nonhuman life is to highlight the usefulness of biodiversity, the interconnectedness of all ecosystems, the moral worth of nonhuman beings, or the suffering induced by human actions. These reasons are significant, and we rely on them in our projects.

In addition, we propose that designing for and with nonhuman beings is the most exciting, rewarding, intellectually challenging, and consequential approach to creative practice. At the Deep Design Lab, we investigate ethical foundations and practical methods of this approach.⁵ We understand design as preparation for future events that can involve but does not require humans. All living beings can self-design and affect others, acting as niche constructors and ecosystem engineers. Human-driven forms of design produce huge effects but remain a component within this picture. The following diagrams position this approach visually.

The aim of design is in redirection from business as usual towards a preferable destination. Our first diagram shows this by building on existing discussions of future cones.⁶ These cones do not acknowledge that preferences diverge, sometimes dramatically, between different clients. In the context of limited knowledge and vested interests, the dominant control by any one group – and humans increasingly wield excessive powers – will harm the outsiders. To counter this, we argue for

nonhuman participation in all forms of governance, including design.

Today, non-anthropocentric design is rare. Our second diagram extends the comparison of attitudes towards the environment⁷ by linking degrees of human bias to design frameworks. Here, the Unrestrained section contains worldviews that permit environmental exploitation. Attitudes within the Shallow section accept that humans have some ethical responsibilities towards nonhuman life and consider future human generations. This section remains clearly anthropocentric and includes current frameworks such as sustainable development goals, nature capital, nature-based solutions, and ecosystem services. Positions within the Intermediate section allow the exploitation of the environment and its nonhuman inhabitants for serious human needs. They also presume that humans know best and can find solutions to emerging problems. Finally, the worldviews within the Deep section accept that some issues can be more significant than even the most serious human concerns. These attitudes also acknowledge significant limitations of human knowledge and prefer to aim for just processes rather than predefined destinations. This ecocentric position deserves more attention from designers and motivates the work of our group.⁸

We are far from alone in the effort to support nonhuman life. The articles herewith attest to the growing interdisciplinary interest towards more-than-human concerns. Matthew Darmour-Paul, Sophie Canaris, and Danielle Celermajer open the conversation by discussing visual experiences of birds and linking them to forms of social engagement that can lead to flourishing. Kylie Soanes expands on this invitation by discussing many opportunities for multispecies living in urban environments, appealing to the powers of interdisciplinary collaboration and citizen participation.

Furthering this argument, Dan Parker outlines an inclusive design approach that aims to help arboreal wildlife. His technical platform makes current evidence and technology accessible to a broad range of human stakeholders. Wolfgang W. Weisser and Thomas E. Hauck provide further context to forms of design that see nonhuman lifeforms as clients. Their framework includes the needs of urban animals as represented by human scientists and the evidence they collect.

Left page:

A prosthetic habitat-structure for the powerful owl in the System Garden, the University of Melbourne. The project and photo by Deep Design Lab.

Katherine A Dafforn, Laura Airoidi, Melanie Bishop, Tim Glasby, Alex Goad, Emma Johnston, Aria Lee, Mariana Mayer-Pinto, Emily Ravenscraft, Annie Tennant, and Maria Vozzo describe a practical example of such science-based approach to cohabitation in application to urban water edges. They frame their approach as gardening under water. Continuing with the theme of gardening as a strategic concept for cohabitation across scales, Rob Dunn's article discusses the role of microbial life and the evolutionary implications of artificial environments, with consequences for design.

Extending this theme into the realm of architecture, Richard Beckett discusses probiotic and bio-receptive approaches to architecture as a path towards better environmental and human health. Complementing approaches informed by science and engineering, Bawaka Country including Laklak Burarrwanga, Ritjilili Ganambarr, Merrkiyawuy Ganambarr-Stubbs, Banbapuy Ganambarr, Djawundil Maymuru, Kate Lloyd, Sarah Wright, Lara Daley and Sandie Suchet-Pearson emphasise the importance of close relationships with places. Such relationships call for sources of knowledge and wisdom that extend beyond science, incorporating practiced behaviours and the law of Indigenous communities.

Finally, in a stark and important reminder, Paula Arcari, Fiona Probyn-Rapsey, and Hayley Singer recast design and architecture as sources of large scale, relentless and intentional violence towards nonhuman lives and especially animals. In contrast with approaches that emphasise opportunities for cohabitation in urban spaces, this article insists on elimination of practices that normalise and institutionalise killing and suffering.

The articles herein represent a significant statement that would not be possible without the contribution of the Deep Design Lab members, the generosity of the contributing authors, and the vision of the journal's editors. In formulating the topic for this issue, the journal posed a range of open questions. What can humans learn about their own needs by designing for and through the senses of other animals? How can humans communicate with nonhuman clients? What creative opportunities emerge from encounters with clients that live in the air, in the water, or deep in the ground? What would design for all life look like? How can it be fair? The articles highlight some directions, but any substantial improvements will require a major reconsideration of design theory, education, and practice. We hope that you will join us in this effort. ■

Dr Stanislav Roudavski is an academic at the University of Melbourne, who designs for animals, plants, rivers, and rocks as well as humans. His research experiments contribute to knowledge by using scientific evidence and advanced technologies in concert with cultural, political, and historical studies.

Top right page:

Diverging preferences in design. Time flows from left to right. The darker green shows probable pasts as defined by known historical facts. The lighter green outlines the zone of conjectures informed by incomplete information. The lighter shades of grey indicate less likely futures as extrapolated from current practices. The squares suggest that preferable futures of different clients never coincide but always overlap. Diagram by Deep Design Lab.

Bottom right page:

Attitudes towards nonhuman life and design. The range is from the anthropocentric attitudes on the left to the ecocentric attitudes on the right. The white texts highlights examples of design practices. The deep green region on the right is most important but today the shallow approaches are much more common. Diagram by Deep Design Lab.

Notes

¹ Parker, Dan, Kylie Soanes, and Stanislav Roudavski. 2022. "Interspecies Cultures and Future Design." *Transpositiones* 1 (1): 183-236. <https://doi.org/10/gpvfs>; Parker, Dan, Stanislav Roudavski, Thérésa M. Jones, Nick Bradsworth, Bronwyn Isaac, Martin T. Lockett, and Kylie Soanes. 2022. "A Framework for Computer-Aided Design and Manufacturing of Habitat Structures for Cavity-Dependent Animals." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 13 (4): 826-41. <https://doi.org/10/gpggfj>.

² <https://vimeo.com/stanislavroudavski/intelligent-lighting>

³ <https://vimeo.com/stanislavroudavski/sentience>

⁴ Roudavski, Stanislav, and Julian Rutten. 2020. "Towards More-than-Human Heritage: Arboreal Habitats as a Challenge for Heritage Preservation." *Built Heritage* 4 (4): 1-17. <https://doi.org/10/ggpv66>.

⁵ <https://wiki.deepdesignlab.online>

⁶ Voros, Joseph. 2003. "A Generic Foresight Process Framework." *Foresight* 5 (3): 10-21. <https://doi.org/10/d2bj4h>.

⁷ Sylvan, Richard., 1985. *A Critique of Deep Ecology: Part 1*. Canberra: Australian National University; Andrew Vincent. 1993. "The Character of Ecology." *Environmental Politics* 2 (2): 248-76. <https://doi.org/10/dtx3m>; Hultgren, John. 2018. "21st Century American Environmental Ideologies: A Re-Evaluation." *Journal of Political Ideologies* 23 (1): 54-79. <https://doi.org/10/ggvp8h>.

⁸ Roudavski, Stanislav. 2021. "Interspecies Design." In *Cambridge Companion to Literature and the Anthropocene*, edited by John Parham, 147-62. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Anthropocentric		Ecocentric	
Unrestrained	Shallow	Intermediate	Deep
design for killing design for extraction	green design nature-based solutions biodiversity-sensitive design sustainable development ecosystem services	animal-computer interaction net-positive design animal-aided design	more-than-human design ecocentric design interspecies design

Who sees the rainforest?

Words by

Matthew Darmour-Paul,
Sophie Canaris and Danielle Celermajer

In *The World Interior of Capital*, Peter Sloterdijk describes the Crystal Palace, the central feature of the 1851 Great Exhibition in London, as emblematic of a new socio-technical order.¹

Using technologies such as cast iron, glass and serial construction, the gardener and builder Joseph Paxton designed an immersive interior that was thermally separated yet visually connected to its environment. As the palace was reinforcing an imperial project in iron and glass, it was also growing a particular kind of human: the modern liberal subject, at home in a frictionless interiority, safe from the messiness of the outside.

This dual conditioning of built environments and human subjectivities was replicable through the ability to build identical glass boxes anywhere within the empire. From leadlight windows to curtain walls, glass production has transformed the way privileged humans build as well as their understanding of natural processes and themselves.

When one of us (Danielle Celermajer) and her partner came to design and build a house in an intentional multispecies community in southeast Australia², one of their aspirations was to create the experience of immersion in the rainforest canopy. Even with the best intentions to create a flourishing multi-species community, the design process did not fully capture all the stakeholders. The design outcome incorporated large windows wrapped around an upper room that gave the human occupants the impression of being suspended amongst the trees. From the outside however, the windows that reflected the rainforest beyond proved lethal for birds. Birds also had the visual experience of immersion in the rainforest in which they made their lives and into which they flew. But this time the reflected rainforest stunned, injured, or killed them. Despite Danielle and her partner's intention to be attuned to the multispecies world in which they lived; they recognised the windows' visual duality only when birds started to fly into the glass.

The structural elements between panes of glass once served not only as visual reminders of labour and technological skill, but also allowed the glass to have a material quality – to be present in space. This meant that the birds could see and recognise the glass, or at least not misrecognise it as sky or forest. The impacts on birdlife of extensive glazing in cities and developments on the edges of nature reserves is well documented, and shocking – billions die each year.³ Part of the problem is that glazing is conceptualised, designed, and built exclusively for the human inhabitant.

Previous page and next page:

A window with strings visible to birds in Escarpment House, by Virginia Kerridge Architect, photo by Matthew Darmour-Paul.

Above:

BIRDSEYEVUE, exhibition by Feral Partnerships, San Mei Gallery, Brixton, London 2022. Photo by the authors.

In the case of large glass windows (and glass doors), modifications to Australian building regulations have been made to increase the safety of children and humans with impaired vision. The latter was a response to the *Disability Discrimination Act* (1992), which was an outcome of long-term advocacy by people with disabilities to ensure that their existence was not the occasion for injustice. Activists insisted that their experience should be formalised through changes in the built environment. What would be an equivalent process in relation to birds? How can birds advocate within institutions where the rules of participation exclude them from the outset? Does the sound of their bodies crashing into a window count as political advocacy? To suggest that it ought to might seem far-fetched, but part of the advocacy that led to the development and adoption of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities involved people mounting actions to bring the public's attention to how the existing built environment disabled them. The question becomes, should privileged humans in control of regulatory standards pay attention to birds' advocacy? Doing so would require both a dedicated attentiveness to birds' lifeworlds and a broader shift in frameworks of justice, which in the west systematically exclude beings other than humans.⁴

Another of us (Matthew Darmour-Paul) recently opened an exhibition with his collective, *Feral Partnerships*, on various design objects that formalise the presence of birds amidst human houses. Items as diverse as swift and sparrow brick houses, a kingfisher tube, a woodstone house martin nest, a wagtail and dipper nest box, a barn owl nest box for buildings, s bricks, and window alert decals were brought together into a single space.⁵ The review of practice in preparation to the exhibition made clear that there is no shortage of discrete attempts to care for birds at the edges of human houses. Back at Danielle's home, humans found a simple solution to the otherwise lethal glazing: a series of strings draped over the windows that move with the wind and signal to the birds: this is not the rainforest. However, most of these design solutions lack a social agenda rooted in multispecies justice. Consequently, their authors are unable to galvanise a movement toward infrastructural change.

To conclude, designs unaccompanied by new social protocols fail to challenge the often-lethal

status quo. It is necessary to simultaneously create prototypes – new structures that accommodate previously unrecognised bodies – and reimagine protocols – sets of rules for social engagement that can support flourishing of multiple species. Some of the most promising alternative models include convivial conservation,⁶ degrowth,⁷ and half-earth socialism,⁸ to name a few (to the interested reader, all are worth exploring in the context of design). The social challenge is at the heart of a design based ecological project, building new images, objects, and spaces, in part to *unbuild* dominant societal narratives. ■

Matthew Darmour-Paul is a researcher and designer based in Sydney, Australia. His work explores architecture's entanglement within political ecology, ruralisation and the financialisation of nature. He is a cofounder of Feral Partnerships, a collective focused on re-claiming architectural knowledge in an age of rapid biodiversity loss and species extinction as spatial practices in the pursuit of multispecies flourishing.

Sophie Canaris is an architect working at Dunn & Hillam Architects. She has delivered arts and community projects in Sydney, regional New South Wales, and London with a focus on sustainability and adaptive re-use. She sits on the Emerging Architects and Graduates Committee and the Built Environment Committee for the New South Wales chapter of the Australian Institute of Architects.

Danielle Celermajer is a professor of sociology at the University of Sydney, deputy director of the Sydney Environment Institute, and lead of the Multispecies Justice project. Her latest book, *Summertime* (Penguin, 2021) calls for recognition of the multispecies harms of the climate catastrophe. It was shortlisted for the Victorian Premier's Literary Award for nonfiction.

Notes

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² Celermajer, Danielle. 2021. *Summertime: Reflections on a Vanishing Future*. North Sydney: Hamish Hamilton.

³ Klem, Daniel. 2009. "Avian Mortality at Windows: The Second Largest Human Source of Bird Mortality on Earth." In *Proceedings of the Fourth International Partners in Flight Conference: Tundra to Tropics*, edited by Terrell D. Rich, Coro Arizmendi, Dean W. Demarest, and Craig Thompson, 244-51. McAllen: Partners in Flight.

⁴ Celermajer, Danielle, David Schlosberg, Lauren Rickards, Makere Stewart-Harawira, Mathias Thaler, Petra Tschakert, Blanche Verlie, and Christine Winter. 2020. "Multispecies Justice: Theories, Challenges, and a Research Agenda for Environmental Politics." *Environmental Politics* 30 (1-2): 119-40. <https://doi.org/10/ghd4fd>.

⁵ See the links to these examples in the online version of the article <https://feralpartnerships.com/>
<https://www.birdbrickhouses.co.uk/brick-nesting-boxes/nesting-boxes/>
<http://www.vivarapro.co.uk/WoodStone-kingfisher-tunnel>
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<https://actionforswifts.blogspot.com/p/fireproof-s-bricks.html?pref=tw>
<https://www.britishbirdfood.co.uk/other-accessories/protection-and-security/window-bird-alert-wild-bird-food-feeders-and-accessories>

⁶ <https://convivialconservation.com/>

⁷ D'Alisa, Giacomo, Federico Demaria, and Giorgos Kallis, eds. 2015. *Degrowth: A Vocabulary for a New Era*. New York: Routledge.

⁸ Vettese, Troy, and Drew Pendergrass. 2022. *Half-Earth Socialism: A Plan to Save the Future from Extinction, Climate Change, and Pandemics*. London: Verso.

Sharing cities with nature, by design

Words by
Kylie Soanes

As an urban ecologist, I specialise in the science and practice of nature conservation in cities. This strikes most people as unusual. Surely, nature conservation happens out in nature, not among the pigeons and bin chickens? But cities support a surprising diversity of native plants and animals – if you're paying attention.

In 2021, an urban citizen-science project known as the City Nature Challenge recorded a whopping 1,187 species in eastern Melbourne alone, spotting tawny frogmouths, satin moths, leopard slugs, and golden wattles galore. Even rare and protected species call cities home. Our recent research shows Australians share their cities with more than 300 threatened plants and animals, with Melbourne hosting 46 treasures, such as the golden sun moth, growling grass frog, and charming spider-orchid. These species can survive in the most unexpected urban places, from roadsides to golf courses, even airports.

With numbers like that, the urban jungles are the perfect place to combat the biodiversity extinction crisis while re-engaging humans with nature. Of course, city-living is challenging – especially when those cities weren't designed for you. Yet still, nature persists. Imagine what could

Previous page:

A wide range of native species call cities home, photo by Kylie Soanes.

Left:

A rope ladder built across the Hume Freeway allows the endangered squirrel glider to cross safely, photo by Kylie Soanes.

be achieved if we designed deliberately with nature in mind? Take the swift parrot. Each winter, these critically endangered birds migrate from their breeding grounds in Tasmania to warmer feeding grounds on the mainland. Flocks are often sighted gorging on the flowering gums popular in city parks, backyards, and streetscapes. It's an excellent example of how urban environments provide important resources for threatened species. Unfortunately, there's a catch. After negotiating the treacherous journey across the Bass Strait, approximately 2% of the already dwindling population die every year after colliding with windows and buildings. Imagine if taking advantage of urban resources didn't come at such a cost?

Another urban wonder is the teddy bear bee. Not only is this aptly named fuzz-ball extremely charismatic, but its unusual method of 'buzz pollination' – using intense vibrations to shake pollen loose – is essential for native plants like flax lilies and guinea flowers. Teddy bear bees thrive on urban gardens: but they need somewhere safe to nest. Like many Australian bees, they do not form hives but are 'solitary nesters', burrowing tunnels in bare soil and clay. But natural materials such as these are scarce in cities, removed in favour of sleek lines, impenetrable surfaces, and tidy open spaces.

Sometimes, simple solutions do the trick. The squirrel glider (the sugar glider's stockier cousin) is an incredible aeronaut, soaring from tree to tree with the help of a skin fold between front and rear limbs. But many roads are a gap too far. To solve this problem, we worked with road agencies and engineers to design 'rope ladders' and 'stepping-stone poles' over the Hume Freeway, allowing gliders to cross safely. My PhD research evaluated their success, with wildlife cameras recording more than 10,000 possums and gliders using the structures. Combining engineering with ecology allowed us to design and test novel approaches, and such structures are now widely adopted.

Novel interventions for nature in cities are on the rise – from insect hotels embedded in walls, pollinator gardens on roadsides, floating wetlands in city rivers, even artificial perches to replace lost trees. However, efforts are still largely constrained to pockets of ambitious practice, with ecologists and designers often working to solve problems from their separate silos. How can we make such interventions more common, more mainstream, more functional? By bridging disciplinary divides between ecology and design.

These disciplines bring complementary skills to the problem at hand. Ecologists can provide

insights into the species – their needs, habits, and risks, while designers bring frameworks and tools for translating those needs into structures that better mimic the complex geometries, organic materials, and thermal properties of nature, providing broader opportunities for life in cities. By joining forces, the fields could develop entirely new solutions that could not be imagined in isolation. So, in your next project, can you find some space for a teddy bear bee, provide safe passage for swift parrots, or a refuge for the growling grass frog? We have an opportunity to make cities better habitats for humans, and for nature. It will be tragic not to take it. ■

Dr Kylie Soanes is a conservation biologist at the University of Melbourne's School of Ecosystem and Forest Sciences. She previously led the Shared Urban Habitat Project through the National Environmental Science Program working with industry and government to develop a strong evidence base for urban nature conservation.

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Designing custom homes for hollow- dwelling animals

Words by
Dan Parker

The housing crisis – a problem familiar to many architects – affects nonhuman beings too. The shortage of tree hollows is one of many examples.

Globally, thousands of bird and mammal species depend on tree hollows for sheltering from weather, hiding from danger, and raising young. Most of these animals cannot build their own hollows. Instead, they rely on cavities made by woodpeckers, termites, or decay-causing organisms. A tree planted today will not support suitable hollows for decades or even centuries. Urgent action is needed to support hollow-dwelling animals while trees regenerate and mature.¹

Human-made hollows, such as nest boxes, can offer some respite.² But conventional nest boxes encounter issues that parallel the shortcomings of modernist approaches to human housing. Standardisation and mass production make objects cheap and easy to produce but limit opportunities to adjust designs for local conditions. Resulting shapes, materials, and performances of such artificial replacements differ significantly from that of tree hollows. Consequences can be severe when nest boxes overheat,³ break,⁴ or fail to attract target species.⁵

Trained in architecture, I now work with ecologists and designers to overcome the limitations of artificial hollows. Within the interdisciplinary research group, Deep Design Lab, my research pursues habitat-creation projects that respond to local ecologies and cultures. Makers of artificial hollows are increasingly interested in such approaches. For example, recent nest-box designs from the Wildlife Safe Havens project feature artworks by local and Indigenous artists. Other artificial hollows try to look like the arboreal termite-nests in nearby forests. Our research shows exciting opportunities to develop innovative artificial hollows by adopting computational approaches from architectural design.⁶ Until now, these approaches required technical expertise and specialised tools, making them unfeasible within community-led projects.

In response, we are developing the prosthetic hollow configurator: a publicly accessible tool that helps people design custom homes for hollow-dwelling animals. The configurator aims to bridge the gap between two challenges: developing well-performing hollows and encouraging community-based conservation. While online configurators usually aim to sell products such as furniture, Bee Home by Space 10 offers a precedent for how such platforms can serve both humans and other animals. Using opensource technologies, online configurators allow anyone to customise designs to suit their unique circumstances.

Want to install a hollow in your local park or backyard?

Step 1 Design:

Select a target species that lives near you, adjust the shape according to personal preferences, and enter the size of the host-tree for easy installation and stable attachment.

Step 2 Manufacturing:

To build the hollow yourself, enter the dimensions of materials you already have, or select one of the listed materials. The configurator will provide recipes to make organic materials and an augmented-reality template on your smartphone to guide assembly. Alternatively, download the 3D model and connect with a local makerspace to have your hollow built professionally. The configurator lists several digital-fabrication services to help you find an option that suits your time constraints, budget, and other requirements. Each selection you make updates estimates on costs, manufacturing times, lifespans, wastage, and the carbon emissions.

Step 3 Deployment:

Select from installation and monitoring options. These include microclimate sensors, cameras for observing animals inside the hollows, and periodic hollow-inspections by professionals.

This project is an outcome of international collaboration between researchers, industrial partners, land managers, and local councils. We are installing prototypes in the field and testing the platform with communities in south-eastern Australia and northern Italy. Feedback from this testing will inform continual refinement of the configurator's algorithm. At the moment, the configurator provides designs for two species: the powerful owl (*Ninox strenua*) and the boreal owl (*Aegolius funereus*). More sites and species are coming soon.

In the near future, you will be able to upload site-specific data to automate the design of hollows. Using software already available on smartphones, you can 3D scan the host-tree to create a custom-fitted hollow. Machine learning makes it possible to optimise hollows based on 3D scans of habitat structures like tree hollows or termite nests.

This workflow is in active testing. As it stands, the configurator provides a preliminary but practical tool that sets out to benefit more-than-human communities. It supports participatory

design practices and encourages community engagement. For example, its interface is suitable for hollow-building workshops with school children and local friends-of-nature groups. The availability of do-it-yourself and professional options makes the benefits of computationally designed hollows more broadly accessible.

This project is significant as an example that can work for other sites, species, and habitat structures. If you would like to use our techniques or work with nonhuman clients who could benefit, please get in touch. ■

Dan Parker is a designer and researcher in the Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning at the University of Melbourne. His PhD investigates innovative design approaches that can support coexistence between humans and other animals in urban environments.

Previous page:

Boreal owl (*Aegolius funereus*) looking out from nesting hollow, photo by Gary Schultz, Alamy.

Left:

Design, manufacturing, and installation of a prosthetic hollow using the online configurator. Top: Installation of a prosthetic hollow for the boreal owl (*Aegolius funereus*) in northern Italy. Top-middle: Design of the prosthetic hollow on the configurator's webpage. Bottom-middle: Assembly of the prosthetic hollow using the configurator's augmented-reality guide on smartphone. Bottom: Rendering of the prosthetic hollow with a soil-based material from the configurator's recipe list.

Notes

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Animal-aided design

Words by
Wolfgang W Weisser
and Thomas E Hauck

Humans have always lived near other animals, not only when they were ranging the Savanna, but also when they founded the first settlements, or started to live in cities.

It is only in the last hundred years or so that humans systematically separated themselves from nature, not only in thinking, but also physically. An increasing body of evidence now suggests that this separation is not good for humans because it results in a lack of ecosystem services provided by nature as well as in detrimental effects on human health and wellbeing. These effects include an increased risk of allergies, asthma and psychological damage. In contradiction to the common practices of separation, humans have a deep desire to be close to nature. For example, renderings produced for architectural design competitions are often populated by animals (mostly with positive connotations), like singing birds, butterflies or picturesque waterfowl. The city is, however, still commonly perceived as a place for humans only, whereas the supposed place for most animals is in the wilderness outside the city. Consequently, most human planning procedures and architectural design only consider the needs of humans. Because most people nowadays live and work in the city, urban nature is the only nature they experience in their day-to-day lives. Thus, an important way to increase human contact with nonhuman life forms depends on the expansion of urban nature and this implies a need for changing the way we design our cities.

Making nature an integral part of urban planning means going beyond current paradigms by framing other organisms as stakeholders of urban planning and architecture. This requires taking the needs of other organisms seriously and carefully planning for their requirements such as food and shelter. Such planning is important because today's dense cities cannot provide these resources without design.¹ For example, it is not sufficient to hang a nest box and hope that the bird will find enough food. Similarly, if we want a particular bird near our house, we need to design planting that fulfils the needs of this species, otherwise it may not be able to survive in our vicinity.

Animal-aided design is an approach that makes animals integral to the design process. Animal-aided design focuses on the needs of species and aims to integrate these needs into landscape architecture and urban design, to enable new ways of viewing and experiencing urban nature. At the beginning of the design process, humans choose target species to become stakeholders. There are many ways to select such species, in cooperation with all human participants in the planning process, including the developer, client and authorities.² Once target species are selected, designers must become familiar with their lifecycles and requirements, prepared in the form of species portraits with data relevant to planning by biologists. Taking their needs seriously allows us to view the building project through the eyes

of these animals. Designing with lifecycles of nonhuman organisms requires creative solutions that can meet the requirements of animals as well as humans, ideally in a synergic manner. For the designer, the requirements of animals set not just the constraints for the design, but also open possibilities. For example, a dust bath for a bird can be realised in many ways, along a footpath, on a flat roof, or as a separate element in the open space. By designing for both humans and wildlife, the architect also has the task to define forms of future co-habitation between humans and animals.

A world in which animals become an integral part of design challenges humans to think about and define their relationship with nonhuman life. What does it mean to coexist with a beaver if one respects the fact that beavers need to fell trees, eat the wood, and build dams? What do such life habits mean for future designs of parks and gardens? How can we integrate multi-species approaches at the scale of a city quarter or an entire city? Animal-aided design is one of several recent approaches that aim to bring ecological knowledge into architectural design. Casting animals as stakeholders of design processes can help to overcome the long-standing dichotomy between humans and nature that for so long limited appreciation and design of cities. ■

Wolfgang W. Weisser is a biologist and a professor for Terrestrial Ecology at the Technical University of Munich, Germany, where he met Thomas E. Hauck with whom he developed the animal-aided design method. His biological research focusses on the effects of land use on biodiversity, with special attention to insects.

Thomas E. Hauck is a landscape architect who co-founded the planning office Polinna Hauck Landscape+Urbanism and co-holds the professorship for landscape architecture and landscape planning at the Vienna University of Technology.

Previous page:

Sparrow flies out of a facade quarter in an AAD project in Munich, photo by Samuel Inter.

Right:

Graphic by AAD and Sophie Jahnke.

Notes

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Basic Research

Creating an underwater garden

Words by

Katherine A Dafforn, Laura Airoidi, Melanie Bishop,
Tim Glasby, Alex Goad, Emma Johnston, Aria Lee,
Mariana Mayer-Pinto, Emily Ravenscraft, Annie Tennant
and Maria Vozzo

City skylines increasingly feature roofs and walls that are covered in foliage to trap stormwater and moderate internal climates. This approach to greening is now creeping below the waterline as ecologists and designers come together to co-create living seawalls.

Urban sprawl is no longer a land-based problem. Sydney Harbour, like many coastal cities around the world, has sprawling structures extending below the waterline. These structures have modified more seafloor than is occupied by the world's mangrove and seagrass forests causing widespread damage.

Humans design structures such as seawalls for protection of their assets or to support their activities, often with little thought for the habitats lost. These structures can result in ecological deserts, supporting little marine life or become dominated by invasive species. To improve their bioreceptivity, humans can instead co-design these urban structures with nature by blending ecology with innovative engineering.

The redevelopment of East Darling Harbour into Barangaroo is one of the most significant urban renewal projects to date in Sydney, Australia. It covers 22 hectares in total and spans 2.2 kilometres of inner-city foreshore. The site was once part of the hunting and fishing grounds for the Traditional Owners of the land, the Gadigal people of the Eora Nation. The name “Barangaroo” recognises a Cammeraygal woman of the same name. From the 1800s to now, the site housed a mix of industrial and commercial uses until the current redevelopment into offices, dining, entertainment, and outdoor spaces.

Life underwater at Barangaroo has been stressful. The darkness cast by towering skyscrapers and noisy port activities have discouraged many of the fish that would have once lived along this foreshore. Prior to the 1800s there were sandy seafloors sloping upwards to rocky outcrops and swampy wetlands, but these natural habitats have gradually been replaced by an underwater concrete jungle of seawalls and pylons. This construction displaced the burrowing worms, shellfish and shrimp that used to live here. The new human-made surfaces provide poor surfaces for marine life, like seaweeds, oysters and barnacles to grow on, preventing their return.

Since 2015, scientists from multiple universities, state government agencies and the Sydney Institute of Marine Science have been working with designers from Reef Design Lab and architects from Lendlease to co-design a living seawall and an underwater garden at Barangaroo. We have created catalogues of the underwater habitats and species living there to inform the enhancements.

We installed nearly four hundred habitat panels at multiple depths that span Watermans Cove in South Barangaroo. Our panels mimic the rocky reefs and seaweed forests found naturally around Sydney Harbour and include features such as rockpools that trap water during low tide, providing protection from

heat to tiny crabs and worms. Other panels resemble the oyster reefs, seaweed roots, and sponge fingers that are key habitats for animals like snails, limpets, chitons, and fish.

To create these complex features, we used 3D-print moulds and then cast the panels in concrete which included upcycled industry by-products. At Barangaroo, we also enhanced the habitat panels with mixtures of recycled oyster shells sourced from Melbourne fish markets, or sandstone rock. The aim of this enhancement is to reduce our carbon footprint and improve the sustainability of the habitat panels.

A few months after the installation, we planted seaweeds to create an underwater garden and kickstart growth on the panels. The seaweeds are a native brown kelp species called *Ecklonia radiata* that we sourced in collaboration with the engineers, SMC Marine, who installed the habitat panels. SMC Marine maintain pylons at multiple locations, and we took the opportunity to harvest kelp for transplantation to Barangaroo from pylons scheduled for removal. Kelp was collected and planted to create the garden at Barangaroo on the same day. An advantage of sourcing kelp already living nearby Barangaroo is that it has adapted to local conditions and so is more likely to survive after planting.

The underwater garden is now 18-months-old and teeming with life that will eventually be self-sustaining for decades. The shallower panels are visible at low tide, but the deeper panels lie below the waterline to support the animals and plants that can't live out of water. Tiny fish have moved in and taken up residence, baby seaweeds are growing on the panels. We will continue to garden the site for the next four years by monitoring and removing any weeds (invasive species) with support from Infrastructure New South Wales.

The underwater garden is part of the Living Seawalls project that is bringing marine life back to built structures in coastal cities and continues to grow with over 1000 habitat panels installed at more than 16 sites worldwide. Our living seawalls support up to 36% more biodiversity than traditional seawalls¹ and the mosaic of designs provides a variety of homes for unique species.² This project demonstrates that all marine constructions can and should consider benefits to humans and nonhuman species.³ ■

Katherine A Dafforn is an environmental scientist recognised for her contributions to understanding and managing urban impacts in marine systems. She completed her PhD and joined Macquarie University in 2018. She is co-founder of the Living Seawalls project, which is based at the Sydney Institute of Marine Science.

Laura Airoidi is professor chair in ecology and deputy director of the Chioggia Hydrobiological Station at Padova University. She is listed among the top Italian Scientists and in 2019 and 2021 was recognised as a Web of Science Highly Cited Researcher. Her research focus is biodiversity conservation and restoration of urbanised marine environments.

Melanie Bishop is a coastal ecologist with over 15 years of experience researching temperate ecosystems of Australia and the US. Her team's research addresses how these ecosystems operate and respond to change. She is co-founder of the Living Seawalls project, which is based at the Sydney Institute of Marine Science.

Tim Glasby is a principal research scientist with 30 years' experience as a marine ecologist working in temperate marine systems, having been employed as an academic, environmental consultant and a government researcher. His research on marine urbanisation, impact assessment and invasive species is internationally recognised and has influenced numerous researchers and government policies.

Alex Goad is a designer and artist based in Melbourne. Alex completed his Bachelor of Industrial Design at Monash University in 2013 where he developed MARS - Modular Artificial Reef Structure. The project won multiple awards and led to Alex starting Reef Design Lab to continue this work.

Emma Johnston is the deputy vice chancellor (Research) at University of Sydney. She heads the Applied Marine and Estuarine Ecology Lab and has led major projects for industry, government, the Australian Research Council and the Australian Antarctic Science Program on the ecology of human impacts in marine systems.

Aria Lee is a marine ecologist and invertebrate biologist. Her research has focussed on understanding the biology and facilitators for invasive species in urbanised coastal areas. She is the program manager for the Living Seawalls project at the Sydney Institute of Marine Science.

Mariana Mayer-Pinto is a Scientia senior lecturer. She obtained her PhD in Marine Sciences from the University of Sydney, 2009 and holds a MSc in Zoology from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. She is co-founder of the Living Seawalls project, which is based at the Sydney Institute of Marine Science.

Emily Ravenscroft is a development manager. She is passionate about placemaking and enriching life between buildings with thoughtful urban planning, quality building design, landscape and public art. Emily has worked in design, construction and property for 20 years, and has experience across sectors, as an architect, project manager and development manager.

Annie Tennant has a Bachelor of Architecture from UNSW and a Master of Urban Design from the University of California Berkeley. She has over 20 years of experience in property, construction, design and development. Annie is on the Landscape Architecture Advisory Panel for the UNSW Landscape program and is an MS Angel.

Maria Vozzo is a marine ecologist with research interests in marine urban ecology and habitat restoration. Maria is currently a research fellow at CSIRO. Her work is investigating methods to scale up marine habitat restoration. She was previously the program manager of the Living Seawalls.

Previous page:

Fish housing on an artificial structure, the Living Seawalls project, photo by Aria Lee.

Acknowledgements

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Notes

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Homes as evolutionary gardens

Words by
Rob Dunn

The body is a home; it is a house structured by the architecture of bones, skin and organs; a house filled with denizens. Thousands of species, including bacteria, archaea, fungi and even animals populate the human body.

Human life depends on many of these species. Scrubbed free of them, a human body would quickly begin to fail, first due to dysfunctions in digestion, immune health and mental health. Then due to pathogens (microbes on the skin are actually the first line of defence against pathogens). Scientists used to think that the human body possessed only defences against microscopic life. We now know it to have many more attributes that work to favour life than to discourage it. The body is, at once, a home and a gardener. It simultaneously seeds some species, weeds others, and works to foil the evolution of yet more dangerous forms.

The sophistication of our bodily home stands in contrast to the majority of houses humans now build. Over thousands of years, vernacular houses were built in ways that responded to the environment and its climatic conditions as well as to the species that were at hand. Where lions were present, houses were built so as to make them easier to defend. Where mosquitoes were present, houses were built to make it more difficult for them to enter bedrooms. These responses of houses to the living world tended to be modest and often focused exclusion, a trend that has accelerated with time.

Once it became clear that some small species could cause disease, attempts to exclude life more fully from houses ensued. These changes were carried out by public health specialists and architects alike. Some of the changes these individuals made to houses and human behaviour inside them were extraordinarily beneficial; these new designs would come to save hundreds of millions or even billions of lives. Changes to water systems, for example, prevented exposure to faecal oral pathogens. Similarly, facilities for hand washing reduced the spread of pathogens from person to person. Meanwhile, the advent of vaccines reduced the prevalence of a subset of pathogens and, in some cases (as with fish, pigs and chickens and apartment-dwelling humans) allowed beings to be housed safely in much higher densities.

Below:

A snapshot of species of bacteria found and grown from individual human belly buttons (each Petri dish is one sample from one person). The different shapes and colours of colonies on different Petri dishes are different species of bacteria. The identity of species living on the human skin is influenced by the use of products, such as antiperspirant, but also by differences from one person to the next in their genes and, specifically, the ways in which those genes influence which foods human bodies provide to skin bacteria.

Yet, more broadly the changes we have made in our houses relative to the rest of life have tended to be maladaptive. Some of these maladaptive choices are global. For example, we have disconnected the styles of houses from their climates in ways that lead to greater reliance on air conditioning (and hence greater global warming and negative impacts on global biodiversity). Other maladaptive choices of humans are more local.

We now know that human mental health benefits from daily connection with nature. For example, children who grow up near large trees are less likely to suffer from anxiety and depression. We also know that the proper functioning of human immune systems requires exposure to a biodiversity of microorganisms, particularly during childhood. The absence of these exposures is associated with Crohn's disease, inflammatory bowel disease, allergy, asthma, rosacea and a vulgar, lurching, bestiary of other disorders, all of which are becoming more common globally. In addition, the acquisition of key gut and skin microbes requires exposure to relevant species (in Western societies, these microbes, including even the microbe babies rely on to digest mother's milk, are being progressively lost). Yet, over the last hundred years humans have increasingly sealed houses ever more tightly and have, also, come to spend more time indoors.

As we look to the next century, I challenge architects to think about how to create homes, other buildings and cities that are more like our bodies, homes that continue to exclude dangerous species, but that also favour beneficial lifeforms, homes more like gardens. As I detail in my book, *Never Home Alone*,¹ there have been successful attempts to garden the bodies of humans (to help, in essence, the work that our bodies are already doing). There have been far fewer attempts to garden homes. What would it look like to have a home that helps us to fend off pathogens but at the same time that favour species that benefit our wellbeing? What would it look like to have homes that were an everyday part of our attempts to be more sustainable, homes in which waste was recycled into energy sources? What would it look like to have homes that were covered with species that bring us joy and species that provide us services? These approaches have costs and potential dangers, of course. For example, a trade-off can exist between sealing a house tightly for energy efficiency and leaving it a little open to let life in. In addition, our understanding of such gardening is often limited. As one measure of this, most of the species currently living in homes have not yet been named by scientists, much less understood.

And our default approach has risks too. We risk creating generations that have not been exposed to the species they need to thrive. We also risk favouring species that sneak past our defences. The problem here is twofold. First, most of the household defences we create are often crude; they tend to kill all species rather than just those we seek to avoid. Second, such defences trigger evolution in the species we would like to keep at bay. Over the last decade our overuse of biocides – be they herbicides, fungicides, pesticides, or antibiotics – has increased. In lock step, the evolution of problem species immune to those same biocides has also increased. Given our current approaches, this contest between our innovation and their evolution is mismatched. They evolve more quickly than we innovate and, as a result, our default houses and cities are, increasingly, populated disproportionately not with beneficial species but instead with resistant problem species; this is the garden of our neglect, a garden of resistant roaches, resistant bacteria, and resistant weeds.

My sense is that there are architects here and there around the world taking up the challenge to create visions for buildings that embrace life and manage evolution in more thoughtful ways. But they're too few. The good news is there are models for what something like this might look like provided by nonhuman species that build homes such as ants and termites. Both ants and termites garden choice species on their bodies and use them to control pathogens in their homes. They also garden edible crops inside their homes. They have created underground homes rich with the life that benefits them. What would it take to imagine future cities rich with the life that benefits us, a future in which we garden constructed environments and, in doing so, engender our own wellbeing? ■

Rob Dunn is a Reynolds professor in applied ecology at NC State University and, also, the senior vice provost for university interdisciplinary programs. He studies the ecology and evolution of daily life, often with a focus on the remote human past and the remote human future. He has written more than a hundred and fifty scientific papers, many articles for general audiences and seven books, most recently, *A Natural History of the Future*.

Note

¹ Dunn, Rob R. 2018. *Never Home Alone: From Microbes to Millipedes, Camel Crickets, and Honeybees, the Natural History of Where We Live*. New York: Basic Books.

Probiotic architecture

Words by
Richard Beckett

Probiotic architecture seeks to conceptualise the building environment not as one that attempts to be healthy through its lack of microbes, but as one that is healthy through its microbiodiversity.

Research into the greening of buildings and infrastructure has predominantly looked to photosynthetic organisms on roofs and walls, validating them – in addition to their pleasant aesthetic – mainly through their contribution to the carbon reduction cycle.

A less discussed agenda of urban biodiversity relates to its fundamental and beneficial role to human health via symbiotic microbiota. Central to this is the growing medical research into the human microbiome and the contemporary understanding of the human as a holobiont. I use the concept of the holobiont as a justification for a new probiotic-design approach that challenges the long-held assumption that fewer microbes equals healthier spaces. In contrast to the modern conception of the human as an island that is biologically distinct from the nonhuman, the holobiont is a multispecies body comprising the host and its multitude of nonhuman microorganisms.¹ These symbiotic microbes play a critical role in metabolic processes, immunoregulation and health outcomes.² Recent evidence associates the lack of microbial exposures in urban environments

with the rise in autoimmune illnesses in developed countries. These epidemics of absence³ or diseases of missing microbes⁴ frame microbes not as germs, but as a fundamental part of the human, a co-evolved entanglement of cells and genes – old friends that we have failed to keep in touch with.⁵

Probiotic architecture explores new ways to (re)integrate a diverse range nonhuman species into architectural structures. This approach considers larger plant species as well as other forms of life including bacteria, archaea, fungi and potentially even viruses. It seeks to conceptualise the building environment not as one that attempts to be healthy through its lack of microbes, but as one that is healthy through its microbial diversity. In this way the building environment becomes analogous to an immune system – one which is

Below:

Probiotic ceramic tiles, embedded with *B.subtilis* – a soil derived microbe that can inhibit MRSA on the tile surface. Top left: Microscale image of porous ceramic material. Top right: microscale image of inoculated microbial communities growing in material pores. Bottom: Geometrical surface details of probiotic pores with porous and non-porous zones. Credit: Richard Beckett

protective but also welcoming to benign and potentially beneficial microbes. Consequently, probiotic architecture might be less concerned with ways to keep nonhuman matter out, and more interested in how to re-introduce microbes into buildings. By integrating habitat opportunities into architectural objects and the spaces they form, probiotic architecture can link microbial communities in the air, water and surfaces of buildings with the skin, nasal passages and gut of the human body, contributing to the health of the holobiont.

At the micro scale, designers can engineer materials to have porosity and chemical properties that encourage the growth of beneficial microbes. Porous ceramics and low pH concretes are among examples of semi-structural architectural materials that can provide microscale niches for microorganisms. These materials can then be inoculated with spores and seeds of desired species or left alone for spontaneous colonisation.⁶

Avoiding uniformity, designers can distribute these materials in response to environmental conditions – including sunlight, shade, and humidity – that can support microbial growth. Here, geometry plays a role too. While smooth, flat dry walls limit growth, three-dimensional textures can facilitate it. These geometries create varying microclimates that can provide protection, retain moisture, trap seeds, accumulate spores and shed them to other surfaces, assisted by air flow.

At the building scale, designers can plan program around horizontal-vertical transitions and slope angles to provide maximum favourable surface areas for biological growth. To support this objective, architecture can engage with large environmental datasets and the emerging sciences of the indoor microbiome including microbial sequencing of buildings and spaces. To work with large amounts of information, architects can use machine learning to maximise biologically receptive niches throughout a building.

In conclusion, a probiotic design approach requires a shift in paradigm that understands the beneficial role that microbes play towards human health. This will require design approaches that operates at multiple scales involving new material approaches, and new typological building programs that promote human-microbe entanglements. Here the criteria for success might depend on more microbes, not less. ■

Richard Beckett is an architect and Associate Professor at the Bartlett, UCL. His research operates at the intersection of computation, biofabrication, and microbial ecologies in buildings and cities. His research on probiotic design won the RIBA President's Research Award in 2021. He has built numerous projects and has been exhibited internationally including *Archilab – Naturalising Architecture*, The Pompidou Centre, and *Nature – Cooper Hewitt Smithsonian Design Museum*.
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Notes

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Caring as Country: attending to the agencies of Country

Words by

Bawaka Country

Including Laklak Burarrwanga, Ritjilili Ganambarr,
Merrkiyawuy Ganambarr-Stubbs, Banbapuy Ganambarr,
Djawundil Maymuru, Kate Lloyd, Sarah Wright, Lara Daley
and Sandie Suchet-Pearson

“They are not voiceless, you know. Animals, that is. But then neither are rocks or winds, tides or plants. They all speak. They all have language and knowledge and Law. They send messages to us; talk to us and to each other. All we have to do is listen; listen and then act”¹

Come with us, here at Bawaka. We invite you to sit on the sand to listen, to attend to Country, to animals and plants and all the beings that belong here. We will share with you some Yolŋu ways of relating to Country from north-east Arnhem Land. If you sit quietly with us, if you pay close attention, you might see for yourself some of what we mean when we say that animals, winds, plants, all the beings and becomings of Country communicate, know and act; that Country has agency. Country is here and in all places in Australia. Even in the big towns and cities waters flow, winds sweep between skyscrapers and Aboriginal people, kinship and connection continue. Now, we sit together on the beach at Bawaka and attend to bāru, listen to crocodile.

Let us introduce ourselves. We are four Yolŋu sisters, Elders, and caretakers for Bawaka Country, together with our daughter and four non-Indigenous academics. We have been a Collective for over 15 years, working together, each from her own place.

When we share knowledge, we do it together, as Bawaka Country. Bawaka Country is homeland. Bawaka Country is the land, the sky, the animals, the plants, the songs that make up Bawaka. They communicate with each other, send messages and shape thought and action. Bawaka Country is human beings, it is humans talking together, it is the sand and the water, the song of the wave on the beach. It is bāru, humans waiting for bāru, songs of bāru, knowledges and lives both independent and co-emergent. So we speak collectively, as far as we can, as human and nonhuman, tangible and intangible, and everything in between.

We invite you to sit with us and attend to Country. Paying attention might require relating to and understanding the world in a different way. And once you do that, there is an imperative to respond and act in different ways too. For Yolŋu, humans are not separate from Country, from animals or plants, from roads or buildings, from the world in which they live. Humans are part of Country and are bound in relations of reciprocity and responsibility. Humans are Country, can speak as Country, and should act responsibly, as Country. We, human and nonhuman, relate to and care for Country as kin – we care as Country.²

To live and know the world in this way speaks to the core of who Yolŋu are. These are issues of Rom, of Yolŋu Law, held through the songspirals (also known as songlines) with depths that we only touch upon here. Yet these knowledges are practical too. Country speaks every day. Its agencies permeate day-to-day existence. What we speak of, what we do, where we sit, how we feel, all emerge from specific

and practical, as well as deep, respectful and responsive, interactions.

This is how Yolŋu think, eat, act, move, dream; this is what we do, who we are, our co-emergent place in the world. The cold wind may move our yarn to a different place; it may bring forth different songs and conversations; we feel it in our bodies, it tells us to hunt and gather particular animals and plants; it brings us together around a fire. And it communicates to nonhumans too, who may migrate, who may begin to nest as bāru does.

We sit here on the beach watching for bāru. Bāru are deeply connected to the Yolŋu people of this land, they are in the paintings, in the dances, in the songs. We are looking now for Nike. This crocodile is part of our family, a protector of our land, Nike knows us, we talk to Nike and Nike talks back.³

We haven't seen Nike for a couple of months now, not since before Christmas, not since the wulma season and the first thunder and lightning. We know that bāru can hear the thunder and then bāru know it's time for nesting. They mate first and then work together to build their nests. Afterwards they sit there all of December, January, February, through the nice soft daytime rain until March when the eggs hatch. If any birds, animals, or humans go to their nest to steal the eggs, bāru get very angry.

As we sit on the beach, watching for Nike, we sit on a plastic mat, sometimes checking phones or googling what comes up in conversation.

||

People exist as part of Country, animals, plants, sands, winds are co-creators of Country. Like humans they too know it, feel it and sing it.

||

At Bawaka and in Yirrkala, where some of us live, there are roads and cars, houses, and other buildings. There's mining too. Sometimes when we talk about Yolŋu connections with Country people think only of animals and plants, things that fit in with mainstream assumptions about Aboriginal identities. We want to tell you that Yolŋu people have a living culture, and Country is always living, always emergent. So those roads, those houses, the sand in the cement, the cement itself, the bauxite that comes out of the mine, that's Country too. They remain in relationship with Yolŋu people.

These relationships need responsible tending to ensure they remain healthy. Humans have responsibilities with and as Country, and to/with/as the built environment. Roads and houses need to be held in balance, accountable to Rom, the Law. What we are saying has implications for design and building across Australia, including urban regions. These places, towns, and cities are always also Country.⁴

It is important that practitioners find ways to come into better, more respectful, relationships with Country and Custodians in the places they live, work, create and build. We cannot say what better means, it will depend on the Country and the Custodians of each place. In every case, it is important to learn about the histories and peoples of that place. Practitioners should listen to the calls of that place and respond respectfully. A call might come from a Custodian offering learning through a book or exhibition, it might be a call to support more Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander practitioners in your field. The calls are many, but you need to be listening and prepared to respond.

Our message here resonates with the call of Gumbaynggirr story holder, Aunty Shaa Smith on mid-north coast New South Wales. She asks those involved in planning, design, urban infrastructure, and development:

“Does our work, the buildings we design or the processes we engage, speak to and support the songlines of the place, the people?” If we want to be creative people, we need to be aware of being destructive, and to be creative in ways that enable us to be in good relationship with Country.⁵

Being in good relationship takes time and we each need to learn what it means where we are. We all need to come respectfully into our relationships and know that we are part of our worlds. Here, we have been sharing with, at and as Bawaka. The messages from Country where you are will be different, held by the beings and sovereignties of that place. But what we can say is that there will be messages, there will be knowledges, there will be responsibilities.

Here at Bawaka, we are related; bāru, the sand, the fire, the wind and humans too; our Country that is us. The call of bāru, of Bawaka, is a call to respond with attentiveness, to take seriously Country's agencies and to act accordingly. We know sometimes it is difficult to hear, to know; but there are specific protocols relating to different places that can guide us. Country is calling for you to respond, always from your place; calling for you to learn, be, do, understand, and attend in response-able ways. ■

The Bawaka Collective is an Indigenous-non-Indigenous, more-than-human collective led by Bawaka Country and including Laklak Burarrwanga, Ritjilili Ganambarr, Merrkiyawuy Ganambarr-Stubbs, Banbapuy Ganambarr, Djawundil Maymuru, Kate Lloyd, Sarah Wright, Lara Daley and Sandie Suchet-Pearson. Also known as the Gay'wu Group of Women, the collective co-authored *Songspirals: sharing women's wisdom of Country through songlines*.

Bawaka Country is the diverse land, water, human and non-human animals (including bāru and the human authors of this chapter), plants, rocks, thoughts, and songs that make up the Yolŋu homeland of Bawaka in North East Arnhem Land, Australia.

Laklak Burarrwanga is a Datiwuy Elder, Caretaker for Gumatj, and eldest sister. As such she has both the right and the cultural obligation to share certain aspects of her knowledge and experiences with others. She has many decades experience sharing this knowledge with children and adults through teaching, art and tourism.

Ritjilili Ganambarr is the second eldest daughter, a Datiwuy elder and caretaker for Gumatj. She works hard on health issues in the community and is passionate about working with mothers and children – teaching and educating them that strong mothers create strong children. She is a weaver and writer/illustrator.

Merrkiyawuy Ganambarr-Stubbs is a proud Yolŋu woman and leader. She has written six books. Her children's books are written in Yolŋu Matha for use in primary schools as Walking Talking texts. She plays an important role in the bilingual education movement working with Yolŋu Elders to develop both-ways learning.

Banbapuy Ganambarr grew up at Gulurruŋa. She is a bilingual student who completed her degree at Bachelor College through the Northern Territory University. Banbapuy is now a senior Indigenous teacher at Yirrkala School. She is an influential author, artist, weaver, and teacher.

Djawundil Maymuru is a Mangalili women, raised by a Gumatj elder. She is a Yolŋu mother and grandmother. She is a co-author of three books and works with Bawaka Cultural Experiences, a highly successful Yolŋu owned and run Indigenous tourism business.

Sarah Wright is Professor of Human Geography at the University of Newcastle. She works in the Philippines with subsistence organic farmers and is a member of the Bawaka Collective and Yandaarra, a Gumbaynggirr-non-Gumbaynggirr collective seeking to shift camp together to care for and as Country where she lives on Gumbaynggirr Country, mid-north coast NSW.

Kate Lloyd is Associate Professor in Human Geography at Macquarie University. Kate's work focuses on several projects which take an applied, action-oriented and collaborative approach to research characterised by community partnerships, co-creation of knowledge and an ethics of reciprocity.

Sandie Suchet-Pearson is Associate Professor in Human Geography at Macquarie University. Her research is in the area of Indigenous rights and environmental management. She is a member of the Bawaka Collective and Yanama Budyari Gumada, a Dharug-non-Dharug Collective aiming to walk with good spirit in caring as Country in western Sydney.

Lara Daley is a research fellow in Human Geography at the University of Newcastle. Her research engages Indigenous-led geographies and ongoing colonisation in urban and semi-urban Indigenous/settler colonial contexts. She is a member of Yandaarra and the Bawaka Collective, two Indigenous-led collaborations focusing on Indigenous sovereignties and Indigenous-led ways of caring for Country.

Right page:
Watching b̄aru at Bawaka

Notes

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Violent architectures

Words by

Paula Arcari, Fiona Probyn-Rapsey
and Hayley Singer

Architecture and design facilitate, modify, or improve existing social and environmental practices, and respond to, encourage, or script new ones. Goals vary, but sustainability is increasingly a key priority in the hope of securing liveable and just futures.

As critical animal studies (CAS) scholars from a cross section of disciplinary backgrounds – creative writing, cultural studies, sociology, feminism, geography, and environmental science – we understand a sustainable and just future as one in which structures, spaces, and materials that perpetuate exploitative animal practices no longer exist.

The design and development of new factory farms, slaughterhouses, meat processing plants, zoos, racing stadiums, and other animal-centred facilities, and improvement of existing operations in the name of efficiency, welfare, and/or increased transparency, continues largely unnoticed except in specialist and local media publications. More visible accolades go to those celebrating convivial multispecies relations through the creation or adaptation of structures that incorporate bird safe design strategies, wetlands, green roofs, tree canopies, microhabitats, noise, and lighting considerations, bioreceptive materials, nesting sites, corridors, and tunnels. These are just some of the strategies gaining prominence that mark a notable and positive shift in values. Unfortunately, this shift is occurring alongside the persistence of hostile designs that accidentally or very deliberately deter, exclude, harm, and kill a range of nonhuman others.

The convivial animal-centric urban developments are hopeful. They go beyond narrow and enduringly anthropocentric conceptions of care that have emerged in urban design and planning,¹ and point to future buildings and entire cities that recognise other animals as equal co-habitants. However, thus far, these considerations for urban nonhumans are largely limited to free-living and (some) commensal animals designated of value in terms of being 'native', iconic, cute, ecologically necessary, or otherwise useful to humans. These are the species people generally like to meet and encounter, or at least tolerate, but as we have pointed out in our analysis of urban rewilding discourses,² there are animals we do not wish to meet or encounter, who remain invisible even in the heart of our cities. 'Pests', 'ferals', and other less desirable critters still present a categorical challenge to the scope of post-human or post-anthropocentric intentions – indicating where lines are clearly drawn – and tend to fair less well in multispecies endeavours. But even they do not fair as badly as the millions of highly commodified animals whose lives and fates are sealed in architectures that are not so much hostile as purposefully violent.

Slaughterhouses, 'process' at least 100,000 animals a day within Greater Melbourne alone, testament to the persistent and unsustainable constitution of edible animals.³ Also within Melbourne, over a million animals per year are used for research

In Melbourne alone,
over a million animals
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in purpose built laboratories and research centres, supplied in part by local breeding operations for beagles, baboons, macaques, rats, mice, and rabbits. Melbourne Zoo (also encompassing Werribee Open Range Zoo and Healesville 'Sanctuary') and Melbourne Sea Life Aquarium, between then contain approximately 8000 animals. Horse-racing, grey hound racing, breeding, and its excesses further contribute to tens of thousands of unwanted, euthanised, and abandoned animals across our cities.

Within ecofeminist and Critical Animal Studies literature, such sites are described as "gulags"⁴ or "mills of brutality."⁵ They are responsible for the routine mistreatment, abuse, injury, death, and "wastage" of massive numbers of animals. This is made possible by structures and practices specifically designed to facilitate the effective and efficient capture, containment, control, separation, isolation, disempowerment, movement, trade, physical harm, and death of nonhuman animals.

However, through a combination of design and narrative, these mechanisms are backgrounded at these sites so that human consumers are detached from the processes that deliver the associated "products." The violence perpetrated at these sites or "shadow places,"⁶ and by the speciesist ideology that constitutes them (which designates animals as usable for food, entertainment, sport, fashion, research, and companionship), is not only physical but also psychological, cultural, epistemic, and ontological, meaning it distorts the experiential basis of an animal's entire existence.⁷

Failing to acknowledge the violence inherent to these sites, or worse, fetishising it (as Jean Hillier notes in reference to the "authentic"

Sites

Slaughterhouses

Factory farms

Meat processing plants

Research laboratories

Racing venues (dogs, horses, other animals)

Equestrian events

Zoos

Petting zoos (that inforce animals as food)

Animal exhibits (dog shows, bull-riding events, rodeos)

Aquariums

Agricultural shows

Practices

Capture (hunting, poaching, trapping, theft)

Containment (cages, enclosures, crates, kennels, tanks, fences, etc.)

Training ('breaking', coercion, reinforcement)

Control (physical and psychological)

Separation, isolation and/or exclusion (from ecology, community, culture, kin)

Trafficking and trading (legal and illegal)

Breeding (captive, forced, selective, AI, genetic modification)

Physical harm (direct and indirect)

Killing (culling, slaughter, euthanasia)

Consumption (literal and visual/emotion — for entertainment, sport and companionship)

history on display at Melbourne’s Kensington Banks housing development on the site of the former Newmarket saleyards and abattoirs), reinforces the anthropocentric agenda that asserts human interests over those of other animals. Such violent architecture could be disassembled, demolished, or even repurposed in ways that serve as cautionary reminders of the suffering these spaces helped to mobilise – ways that pay dues to the “ghostly signals” of place, its “noisy silences and seething absences”, warn of dark pasts never to be repeated⁸, and above all avoid “aestheticized [and commodified] version[s] of history”⁹. This dis/reassembly would be undertaken within a more comprehensive framework of non-speciesist architectural principles, even of interspecies sustainability.¹⁰

Of course, change cannot happen overnight, but it will hopefully accompany the increasing unacceptability of the principles and practices that both constitute and support violent architectures. Just some of these architectures are listed in the accompanying table along with the violent practices enacted against animals they rely on and that in turn demand and shape a host of secondary sites, tools, devices, and design decisions.

One question that presses on us is: What might non-violent architectures, or architectures of sanctuary, look like especially for those commodified animals that we human animals have a duty to care for as the practices that currently prescribe their birth, life, and death are wound back? Bird safe building guidelines, and other measures, are a good start to diminishing the built-in violence that surrounds us, whether acknowledged or not. But we argue that we need to go further, much further. Now. ■

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Fiona Probyn-Rapsey is a professor in the School of Humanities and Social Inquiry at the University of Wollongong. She is the author of *Made to Matter: white fathers, stolen generations*,¹¹ and co-editor of *Animal Death*,¹² *Animals in the Anthropocene: critical perspectives on non-human futures*¹³ and *Animaladies: Gender, Species, Madness*.¹⁴

Hayley Singer is an associate of the Australian Research Council Centre of Excellence for the History of Emotions, and an early career researcher and teaching associate at the University of Melbourne where she also earned her PhD in creative writing. Her fiction, non-fiction, poetry, scholarly writing, and book reviews have been published in Australian journals and anthologies.

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